

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Disclosure of Potential Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Ethical Approval

All procedures performed in this study involving human participants were approved by the Auburn University Institutional Review Board (IRB protocol number: **20-232 EX 2005**) and were conducted in accordance with institutional and ethical research standards.

Informed Consent

In accordance with IRB approval, a waiver of written informed consent was granted. Passive consent procedures were implemented, and youth participants were provided the opportunity to opt out of the survey at any time.

Author Contributions

Each author has made contributions to the work, including the conceptualization and design of the study, data collection, analysis, and interpretation, as well as the drafting and revising of the manuscript. We have reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Angela Mintah, MSW: Led conceptualization and study design; conducted data analysis, manuscript writing and revisions.

Adrienne Duke-Marks, PhD: Principal Investigator of the program, contributed to revisions of the manuscript, provided critical feedback on the manuscript draft.

We declare that this manuscript represents original work, has not been published previously, and is not under consideration for publication elsewhere.

Clinical Trial Registration

Not applicable. This study did not involve a clinical trial requiring registration.